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AN EFFICIENT LUCAS WAVELET GALERKIN METHOD FOR SOLVING TIME-DELAY OPTIMAL CONTROL PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT. Here, we present a numerical scheme to solve optimal control problems with time-varying delay system. This method is based on Lucas wavelets and Galerkin method. Operational matrices of integration and delay for Lucas wavelets are proposed. Then, Galerkin method is used to solve the mentioned problems. Numerical results are included to demonstrate the efficiency of the present technique.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of important class of delay problems is optimal control problems that are used to model many of the phenomena. Furthermore, there are several numerical methods to solve delay optimal control problems such as Variational iteration method [1] and finite difference method [2]. In recent years, the construction and application of different wavelets such as Bernoulli wavelet [3], Fibonacci wavelet [4], Legendre wavelet [5] has been shown to be a powerful mathematical tool for discretization of selected problems.

In this work, we apply the extended Lucas wavelets for solving fractional delay optimal control problems. To this end, we approximate the fractional derivative of the state variables and control variables in terms of these wavelets. We present

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new fractional integration and delay operational matrices for these functions. Then, by employing the operational matrices and Galerkin method, the problems under consideration are converted into systems of algebraic equations. The validity of the established methods is studied in one example.

2. LUCAS WAVELETS AND PROPERTIES

The Lucas wavelets are defined over the interval $[0, 1]$ in [6]. We present a new presentation of these functions in the following form

$$(2.1) \quad \psi_{n,m}(t) = \frac{2^{\frac{k-1}{2}}}{\sqrt{w_m}} \tilde{L}_m(2^{k-1}t - n + 1) \chi_{[\frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}}, \frac{n}{2^{k-1}}]}(t), \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}, \quad m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1,$$

and $\chi_{[\frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}}, \frac{n}{2^{k-1}}]}(t)$ is the characteristic function, $w_m = \int_0^1 \tilde{L}_m^2(t) dt$, and $\tilde{L}_m(t)$, $m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$ denotes the Lucas polynomials. $n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}$ and k is a positive integer. Also, $\tilde{L}_0(t) = 2$, $\tilde{L}_m(t) = \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \frac{m}{m-i} \binom{m-i}{i} t^{m-2i}$.

2.1. Integration operational matrix of Lucas wavelets. Let

$$\Psi(t) = [\psi_{1,0}, \psi_{1,1}, \dots, \psi_{1,M-1}, \psi_{2,0}, \psi_{2,1}, \dots, \psi_{2,M-1}, \dots, \psi_{2^{k-1},0}, \dots, \psi_{2^{k-1},M-1}]^T,$$

be Lucas wavelets vector. The integration operational matrix of Lucas wavelets \tilde{P} is defined as $\int_0^t \Psi(s) ds \simeq \tilde{P}\Psi(t)$, each of element of this matrix is derived in the following process

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{n,m}(t) &= \frac{2^{\frac{k-1}{2}}}{\sqrt{w_m}} \tilde{L}_m(2^{k-1}t - n + 1) \chi_{[\frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}}, \frac{n}{2^{k-1}}]}(t) \\ &= \frac{2^{\frac{k-1}{2}}}{\sqrt{w_m}} \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \sum_{j=0}^{m-2i} \binom{m-i}{i} \frac{m}{m-i} 2^{kj-j} t^j (1-n)^{m-2i-j} \chi_{[\frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}}, \frac{n}{2^{k-1}}]}(t). \end{aligned}$$

Now, using the above relation, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^t \psi_{n,m}(s) ds &= \frac{2^{\frac{k-1}{2}}}{\sqrt{w_m}} \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \sum_{j=0}^{m-2i} \binom{m-i}{i} \frac{m}{m-i} 2^{kj-j} (1-n)^{m-2i-j} \int_0^t s^j \chi_{[\frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}}, \frac{n}{2^{k-1}}]}(s) ds \\ &= \frac{2^{\frac{k-1}{2}}}{\sqrt{w_m}} \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \sum_{j=0}^{m-2i} \binom{m-i}{i} \frac{m}{m-i} 2^{kj-j} (1-n)^{m-2i-j} \theta_j(t), \end{aligned}$$

$$\theta_j(t) = \int_0^t s^j \chi_{[\frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}}, \frac{n}{2^{k-1}}]}(s) ds = \int_{\frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}}}^t s^j ds \chi_{[\frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}}, \frac{n}{2^{k-1}}]}(t) + \int_{\frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}}}^{\frac{n}{2^{k-1}}} s^j ds \chi_{[\frac{n}{2^{k-1}}, 1]}(t),$$

Here, we expand this function in terms of Lucas wavelets as $\theta_j(t) = \sum_{s=1}^{2^{k-1}} \sum_{p=0}^{M-1} b_{s,p} \psi_{s,p}(t)$. Therefore, we achieve $\int_0^t \psi_{n,m}(s) ds = \sum_{s=1}^{2^{k-1}} \sum_{p=0}^{M-1} \Theta_{s,p}^{n,m} \psi_{s,p}(t)$,

$$(2.2) \quad \Theta_{s,p}^{n,m} = \frac{2^{\frac{k-1}{2}}}{\sqrt{w_m}} \sum_{i=0}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \sum_{j=0}^{m-2i} \binom{m-i}{i} \frac{m}{m-i} 2^{kj-j} (1-n)^{m-2i-j} b_{s,p}$$

2.2. Delay operational matrix of Lucas wavelets. We suppose that $\tau = \frac{s}{2^{k-1}}$, then $\Psi(t - \tau) = \tilde{D}\Psi(t)$, $t > \tau$. For this approach, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{n,m}(t - \tau) &= \begin{cases} \frac{2^{\frac{k-1}{2}}}{\sqrt{w_m}} \tilde{L}_m(2^{k-1}(t - \tau) - n + 1), & \frac{n-1}{2^{k-1}} \leq t - \tau < \frac{n}{2^{k-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\ &= \begin{cases} \frac{2^{\frac{k-1}{2}}}{\sqrt{w_m}} \tilde{L}_m(2^{k-1}t - (n + s) + 1), & \frac{n-1+s}{2^{k-1}} \leq t < \frac{n+s}{2^{k-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} = \psi_{m,n+s}(t). \end{aligned}$$

3. NUMERICAL METHOD

Here, we consider

$$(3.1) \quad \begin{cases} X'(t) = A(t)X(t) + B(t)X(t - \tau) + G(t)U(t) + H(t)U(t - \tau), & t \in [0, 1], \\ X(0) = X_0, \\ X(t) = \phi_1(t), & t \in [-\tau, 0), \\ U(t) = \phi_2(t), & t \in [-\tau, 0). \end{cases}$$

where $X(t) \in R^l$, $U(t) \in R^q$, ($l \geq q$) $A(t)$, $B(t)$, $G(t)$ and $H(t)$ are continuous matrices with appropriate dimensions, X_0 is constant vector and $\phi_1(t)$ and $\phi_2(t)$ are known functions defined on the interval $[-\tau, 0)$. In Eq. (3.1), we derive $X(t)$ and optimal control $U(t)$ which are satisfied in conditions of problem while extremizing J

$$(3.2) \quad J = X^T(1)Q(1)X(1) + \int_0^1 [X^T(t)Q(t)X(t) + U^T(t)R(t)U(t)]dt,$$

where $Q(t)$, $R(t)$ are matrix functions with appropriate dimensions. Also, $Q(t)$ is a symmetric positive-semi-definite matrix and $R(t)$ is a symmetric positive-definite matrix. Assume that $X(t) = [X_1(t), X_2(t), \dots, X_l(t)]^T$, $U(t) = [U_1(t), U_2(t), \dots, U_q(t)]^T$, and $[\tilde{\Psi}_l(t) = I_l \otimes \Psi(t)$, $\tilde{\Psi}_q(t) = I_q \otimes \Psi(t)$, where I_l, I_q are the l -dimensional and q -dimensional identity matrices and \otimes denotes Kronecker product. Moreover $\tilde{\Psi}_l(t)$ and $\tilde{\Psi}_q(t)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, l$, $j = 1, 2, \dots, q$ are $l2^{k-1}M \times l$ and $q2^{k-1}M \times q$ matrices. We approximate as $X'_i(t) = X_i^T \Psi(t)$, $U_j(t) = U_j^T \Psi(t)$. Therefore, we get $X'(t) = X^T \tilde{\Psi}_l(t)$, $U(t) = U^T \tilde{\Psi}_q(t)$, and for $X(t)$, we can see that $X(t) = X^T \hat{P} \tilde{\Psi}_l(t) + \hat{E}^T \tilde{\Psi}_l(t)$, where $\hat{P} = I_l \otimes \hat{P}$, $\hat{E} = I_l \otimes \hat{E}$ and $X(0) \simeq \hat{E}^T \Psi(t)$. Also, using delay operational matrix of Lucas wavelets, we expand $X(t - \tau)$ and $U(t - \tau)$ in terms of them as

$$(3.3) \quad X(t - \tau) = \begin{cases} \phi_1(t - \tau), & 0 \leq t \leq \tau \\ X^T \hat{P} \hat{D}_l \tilde{\Psi}_l(t) + \hat{E}^T \hat{D}_l \tilde{\Psi}_l(t), & \tau \leq t \leq 1, \end{cases} \quad U(t - \tau) = \begin{cases} \phi_2(t - \tau), & 0 \leq t \leq \tau \\ U^T \hat{D}_q \tilde{\Psi}_q(t), & \tau \leq t \leq 1, \end{cases}$$

TABLE 1. Comparison of the value of J , in Example.

Numerical methods	J
Variational iteration method [1]	3.1091
Finite difference method [2]	3.102519
Present technique (k=3, M=6)	3.10078
Present technique (k=3, M=8)	3.10101
Exact value	3.1017

where $\widehat{D}_q = I_q \otimes \widetilde{D}$, $\widehat{D}_l = I_l \otimes \widetilde{D}$ and \widetilde{D} is delay operational matrix of Lucas wavelets. Moreover, we approximate $A(t), B(t), G(t)$, and $H(t)$. We substitute the approximations in the system then we derive $\widetilde{\Phi}(t)$. The resulting equation can be solved using Galerkin method $Y = \langle \widetilde{\Phi}, \Psi \rangle$. Also, we substitute the mentioned approximations and the performance index J , so we have $J^* = J + \lambda^T Y$, where $\lambda = [\lambda_{n,m}]$ $n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{k-1}$, $m = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$ are the unknown multipliers coefficients. For deriving extremum of J^* , the necessary condition is that the following equations hold $\frac{\partial J^*}{\partial X} = 0$, $\frac{\partial J^*}{\partial U} = 0$, $\frac{\partial J^*}{\partial \lambda} = 0$. We can solve these equations using "FindRoot" package in Mathematica software.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Example. Consider $J = \frac{3}{2}X^2(2) + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^2 U^2(t)dt$, subject to the time-delay system

$$X'(t) = X(t) + X(t-1) + U(t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq 2, \quad X(t) = 1, \quad -1 \leq t \leq 0,$$

in which the analytic solution for $U(t)$ is $U(t) = \begin{cases} \delta(e^{2-t} + (1-t)e^{1-t}), & 0 \leq t \leq 1, \\ \delta e^{2-t}, & 1 \leq t \leq 2. \end{cases}$ and with $\delta = -0.3932$, $J \simeq 3.1017$ [4]. This example solved by several numerical techniques such as variational iteration method [1] and finite difference method [2] with $h = 0.01$. In Table 1, these numerical results are compared to the results obtained using the present method for different values of k, M .

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